

Isolation and Identification of *Staphylococcus aureus* in Febrile Illness Cases.

Jayanta Deb^{1*}, Seemanti Debnath²

¹PhD scholar (GLA University Mathura) and Laboratory technician of Central laboratory, AGMC & GBP Hospital, Kunjaban-799006, Agartala, Tripura, Northeast India.

²Senior Resident, Department of Microbiology, AGMC & GBP Hospital, Kunjaban-799006, Agartala, Tripura, Northeast India

ABSTRACT

Background: *Staphylococcus aureus* is a primary source of hospital and community-acquired infections, and methicillin-resistant strains (MRSA) pose a substantial global health threat due to their antibiotic resistance. The purpose of this study was to establish the frequency of *S. aureus* and MRSA among febrile patients, assess their antibiotic resistance profiles, and compare susceptibility patterns between MRSA and non-MRSA isolates. **Method:** Cross-sectional research was undertaken at AGMC and GBP Hospital from January to July 2024. Blood samples from 100 febrile patients were cultured, and isolates were identified using normal microbiological procedures. The Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion technique was used to determine antibiotic susceptibility, and resistance patterns were examined with Chi-square and Fisher's exact tests. **Result:** *S. aureus* was identified from 22% of patients, with MRSA accounting for 41%. MRSA isolates were completely resistant to ceftazidime, ciprofloxacin, and azithromycin, with significant resistance to co-trimoxazole and levofloxacin. In contrast, vancomycin, linezolid, and gentamicin remained effective against the majority of isolates. Statistical analysis found substantial variations in resistance patterns between MRSA and non-MRSA strains ($p < 0.05$). **Conclusion:** MRSA isolates have a multidrug resistance profile, restricting treatment choices. Continued surveillance, antimicrobial stewardship, and targeted infection control methods are critical for preventing the spread of resistant *S. aureus* strains.

Keywords: Febrile Illness.

INTRODUCTION

Staphylococcus aureus is a major human pathogen that causes a wide range of clinical diseases, including superficial skin infections, bacteraemia, pneumonia, and sepsis¹. The organism's exceptional adaptability and virulence mechanisms have propelled it to the forefront of nosocomial and community-acquired infections (CAI's)². Molecular typing investigations have shown genetic variability among *S. aureus* isolates, indicating the capacity to acquire and spread antibiotic resistance genes³. Hospitalized patients, particularly those having surgery or invasive treatments, are more susceptible to infection due to weakened immunity and extended hospital stays⁴. The rise of multidrug-resistant strains, such as methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA), has presented a

significant challenge to infection control and therapeutic management globally⁵. Environmental reservoirs, healthcare staff, and hospital air have all been identified as possible sources of *S. aureus* transmission within hospitals⁶. The nasal carriage of *S. aureus* among healthcare personnel contributes significantly to the spread of MRSA in healthcare settings. Post-surgical and wound infections caused by *S. aureus* have been shown to have significant rates of antibiotic resistance, complicating treatment results⁸. Advanced methods, including PCR, MALDI-TOF MS, and molecular tests, are increasingly being used to distinguish MRSA from methicillin-susceptible bacteria⁹. Recent investigations have shown that phenotypic and genotypic resistance features coexist in *S. aureus*, suggesting the complexities of antibiotic resistance¹⁰. *S. aureus*

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infections in the musculoskeletal, burn wound, and circulation have different phenotypic and genotypic profiles, which influence patient morbidity and mortality^{11,12}. Regional studies from Africa and Asia corroborate MRSA's burden as a severe public health concern with important clinical and epidemiological consequences^{13,14}. The rise of vancomycin-resistant *S. aureus* (VRSA) has been observed in several regions of the world, raising severe concerns about restricted treatment choices¹⁵. Infections in immunocompromised individuals, such as those with cystic fibrosis, demonstrate *S. aureus* adaptability and interactions with co-infecting bacteria such as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*¹⁶. Regional surveillance data from Vietnam and South Africa highlight the presence of MRSA with diverse resistance phenotypes and genotypes^{17,18}. Furthermore, the clinical consequences of *S. aureus* bacteraemia are determined by the strain type, antibiotic resistance, and patient-related risk factors¹⁹. Overall, MRSA is a major worldwide health problem because to its high resistance rates, transmission dynamics, and link to catastrophic clinical consequences²⁰.

Methodology

Study type: Cross sectional study

Study duration: January to July 2024

Study location: Individuals who visited in different outpatient department (OPD) of AGMC & GBP Hospital's irrespective of their age and gender.

Ethics: Informed consent was obtained before utilizing biological samples, and the study was authorized by the Institutional Human Ethics Committee (Ethical: 4311/2022).

Inclusion and Exclusion criteria of study participants: This research included participants who had a fever for at least 0-5 days did not begin antibiotic medication. Participants who begin antibiotic medication they are excluded from this study.

Sample collection: Venous blood samples (05ml for adult and 01 ml for infants and paediatrics) were collected in brain heart infusion broth (BHI) from all participants. A comprehensive questionnaire was

completed by each patient, which asked about their age, gender, and any medications they were currently taking. Blood samples were collected from 100 consecutive febrile patients²¹.

Culture: Blood sample were incubated in the BACT/ALEART machine after positive indication subculture was done on MacConkey's agar medium, sheep blood agar media (10%) Mannitol salt agar (MSA) medium After a 24-hour aerobic incubation period at 37°C, the plates were checked for growth. By using recognized techniques, including colony morphology, pigment production, gram staining, the catalase test, the slide and tube coagulase test, the modified Hugh and Leifson (O/F) test, and mannitol fermentation, the *Staphylococcus aureus* that was isolated from the blood samples was identified⁷.

Antibiotic sensitivity test: Moller Hinton agar (MHA) was used for performing the antibiotic disc diffusion procedure, with 0.5 MacFarland maintained and incubated overnight in a bacteriological incubator. The Kirby-Bauer method was used to examine the susceptibility of 22 bacterial strains. The eight antibiotics studied included gentamicin (GEN), ciprofloxacin (CIP), co-trimoxazole (COT/SXT), vancomycin (VAN), linezolid (LNZ), doxycycline (DOX), cefoxitin (CX), levofloxacin (LEV), and azithromycin (AZM). The agar dilution method was used to determine the MIC values of the antimicrobials under investigation. *S.aureus* ATCC 29213 used as the quality control strain in the MIC experiments¹⁷.

RESULT

The study involved 100 patients in total. Of these, 78 patients (78%) had negative test results, whereas 22 patients (22%) had positive findings. This suggests that around one-fifth of the participants in the research had good results. Six (27.3%) of the positive cases were male, and 16 (72.7%) were female, according to the gender distribution.

According to the results, women were more likely than men to be positive. The Emergency Medicine Ward (EMW) and the Female Medicine Ward (FMW) contributed the most isolates (23%), with 5 isolates each, out of the 22 positive cases. Next in line were the Male Medicine Ward (MMW), Neonatal Intensive

Care Unit (NICU), and Paediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU), each of which had two isolates (9%), followed by the Medical Intensive Care Unit (MICU) with three isolates (14%).

There were fewer isolates from the Obstetrics ward (OBS) with one isolate (5%) and the Adult Intensive Care Unit (AICU) and Female Orthopaedic Ward (F-ortho) with one isolate each (4%). Figure 1. Nine isolates were found to be MRSA from the 22 positive patients. Of these, 7 (77.8%) were from female patients and 2 (22.2%) were from male patients, indicating that MRSA was more common in female patients.

Figure 01: Distribution of isolated *Staphylococcus aureus*

Antibiotic pattern of isolated *Staphylococcus aureus*

Vancomycin and linezolid had 100% sensitivity with no resistance, making them the most effective antibiotics, according to antibiotic susceptibility tests. Compared to levofloxacin and Doxycycline, both shown 86% sensitivity and 14% resistance. Gentamicin showed 18% resistance and 82% sensitivity. Cefoxitin showed 59% sensitivity and 41% resistance, azithromycin showed 55% sensitivity and 45% resistance, and co-trimoxazole showed 64% sensitivity and 36% resistance, indicating moderate susceptibility. With 45% sensitivity and 55% resistance, ciprofloxacin demonstrated the least amount of effectiveness (Table 1).

Antibiotic	Sensitive	Resistance
Doxycycline	86%	14%
Vancomycin	100%	00
Linezolid	100%	00
Cefoxitin	59%	41%
Co-Trimoxazole	64%	36%
Ciprofloxacin	45%	55%
Levofloxacin	86%	14%
Gentamicin	82%	18%
Azithromycin	55%	45%

Antibiotic pattern of isolated MRSA

The results of the MRSA isolates' antibiotic susceptibility profile were inconsistent. The most effective treatment was linezolid, which showed sensitivity in 89% of isolates. Doxycycline showed 56% sensitivity, whilst vancomycin and gentamicin were effective in 67% of isolates. On the other hand,

100% of isolates exhibited complete resistance to cefoxitin, ciprofloxacin, and azithromycin. Additionally, significant resistance to levofloxacin (89%) and co-trimoxazole (78%) was noted (Table 2).

Antibiotic	Sensitive	Resistance
Doxycycline	56%	44%
Vancomycin	67%	33%
Linezolid	89%	11%
Cefoxitin	00	100%
Co-Trimoxazole	22%	78%
Ciprofloxacin	00	100%
Levofloxacin	11%	89%
Gentamicin	67%	33%
Azithromycin	00	100%

Statistical analysis: MRSA isolates and normal *Staphylococcus* isolates were analysed for antibiotic resistance patterns. Chi-square and Fisher's exact tests were used in the statistical analysis, which showed that all tested drugs had significant differences in resistance ($p < 0.05$). When compared to normal

Staphylococcus, MRSA isolates showed noticeably greater rates of resistance, with total resistance to cefoxitin, ciprofloxacin, and azithromycin. These results demonstrate MRSA's multidrug resistance and emphasize the necessity of carefully choosing potent antibiotics for clinical therapy (Table 03).

Antibiotic	MRSA Resistant (%)	Staph Resistant (%)	p-value	Significant Difference
Doxycycline	44	14	< 0.00001	Yes
Vancomycin	33	0	< 0.00001	Yes
Linezolid	11	0	0.002	Yes
Cefoxitin	100	41	< 0.00001	Yes
Co-Trimoxazole	78	36	< 0.00001	Yes
Ciprofloxacin	100	55	< 0.00001	Yes
Levofloxacin	89	14	< 0.00001	Yes
Gentamicin	33	18	0.023	Yes
Azithromycin	100	45	< 0.00001	Yes

DISCUSSION

Staphylococcus aureus was found in 22% of the patients in this study, with a higher prevalence in females (72.7%) than in males (27.3%). Previous studies have shown that female patients were more likely to be colonized or infected with *S. aureus*^{7,8}. The distribution of isolates across hospital wards showed that the Emergency Medicine Ward (EMW) and Female Medicine Ward (FMW) contributed the highest number of isolates (23% each), reflecting the higher risk of nosocomial acquisition in high-turnover and high-contact units, which is consistent with findings from Mulu et al. (2012) and Poorabbas et al. (2015)^{1,4}.

09 (41%) of the 22 positive cases were diagnosed as MRSA, primarily from female patients. The prevalence of MRSA in females is consistent with prior research demonstrating gender variations in MRSA colonization and infection^{2,10}. The prevalence of MRSA in different wards, including intensive care units, highlights its importance as a nosocomial infection with the potential for fast spread^{6,17,19}.

The antibiotic susceptibility profile of general *S. aureus* isolates revealed great sensitivity to vancomycin and linezolid (100%), moderate sensitivity to doxycycline (86%), levofloxacin (86%), and gentamicin (82%), and significant resistance to ciprofloxacin (55%) and azithromycin (45%). These

findings are consistent with studies from Iran, Ethiopia, and Vietnam that found vancomycin and linezolid to be the most effective drugs against *S. aureus*^{15,17}. Co-trimoxazole, cefoxitin, and azithromycin showed considerable resistance, indicating that these drugs should be used with caution in empirical therapy^{3,13}. MRSA isolates had a multidrug resistance phenotype, with full resistance to cefoxitin, ciprofloxacin, and azithromycin, as well as significant resistance to co-trimoxazole (78%) and levofloxacin (89%). Linezolid (89% sensitivity), vancomycin (67% sensitivity), and gentamicin (67% sensitivity) remained the most effective treatments. Significant differences in resistance patterns between MRSA and general *S. aureus* ($p < 0.05$ for all tested antibiotics) highlight the increased therapeutic challenges posed by MRSA. This supports previous reports of multidrug-resistant MRSA in hospital settings^{9,17,18}. The high prevalence of MRSA and its resistance to multiple commonly used antibiotics highlights the importance of routine antimicrobial susceptibility testing, infection control measures, and careful antibiotic selection to prevent the spread of resistant strains^{15,20}. Furthermore, ongoing surveillance and molecular characterisation of MRSA are critical for identifying local resistance trends and directing optimal clinical therapy^{2,16}.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that *Staphylococcus aureus* infections remain a major problem, with MRSA accounting for a sizable number of cases. MRSA isolates had a multidrug resistance profile, with full resistance to cefoxitin, ciprofloxacin, and azithromycin, although vancomycin, linezolid, and gentamicin remained effective. The increased prevalence of MRSA among female patients and in high-contact wards emphasizes the importance of targeted infection control measures. Routine antimicrobial susceptibility testing, careful surveillance, and prudent antibiotic usage are needed to avoid the emergence of resistant strains and guarantee efficient therapeutic therapy.

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